

A. Reviewer's Report

The article titled "*Cash Transfer Program Enrolment and Retention of Girls in Schools of South Sudan: A Case Study of Yambio County, Western Equatoria State*" explores the impact of cash transfer programs on the enrolment and retention of girls in schools, focusing on the context of Yambio, South Sudan. Authored by Jonathan Bage John, the study employs a qualitative research approach, utilizing both narrative and content analysis to analyze data collected from 147 respondents, including parents and student beneficiaries of the cash transfer program.

The introduction sets the stage by highlighting the importance of education, especially for girls, in regions like sub-Saharan Africa, where access to education remains a challenge. The article positions cash transfer programs as interventions aimed at breaking economic barriers hindering access to education, with a specific focus on conditional cash transfer (CCT) programs. However, it critiques the lack of awareness within the South Sudanese government regarding the effects of cash transfer programs on enrolment and retention.

The background section provides a comprehensive overview of CCT programs, tracing their origins from Latin America to Africa. It discusses the objectives and design principles of CCTs, emphasizing their potential to alleviate poverty and enhance human capital investment. The article also delves into the theoretical frameworks underpinning the study, namely Social Capital Theory and Maslow's Theory of Needs, to provide a conceptual basis for understanding the dynamics of cash transfer programs.

Throughout the article, the author presents various studies and evaluations of CCTs conducted globally, highlighting both their short-term impacts on poverty reduction and long-term implications for education and health outcomes. These studies serve to contextualize the discussion within the broader literature on social protection and development interventions.

In the conclusion, the study findings suggest that cash transfer funds significantly influence the enrolment and retention of girls in schools in Yambio, South Sudan, primarily by enabling access to scholastic materials and supporting household needs. However, the article also acknowledges instances of fund misuse and identifies certain conditionalities that may inadvertently contribute to school dropout. Moreover, the effectiveness of monitoring and evaluation processes in ensuring program success is noted, albeit with some irregularities highlighted.

The recommendations put forward by the study underscore the need for parental responsibility in directing cash transfer funds towards education-related expenses. Additionally, stakeholders are urged to review program conditionalities to mitigate negative impacts on girls' education, such as dropout rates. Furthermore, calls are made for enhanced monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to ensure the accountability and effectiveness of cash transfer initiatives.

Overall, the article provides valuable insights into the role of cash transfer programs in promoting girls' education in South Sudan. It contributes to existing literature by offering empirical evidence and practical recommendations for policymakers and practitioners. However, it also raises important questions regarding the implementation and monitoring of such programs, calling for further research and refinement of strategies to maximize their impact on educational outcomes.

The conclusions drawn in the article generally align with previous research on the positive effects of cash transfer programs on education outcomes, particularly for girls. However, the acknowledgment of potential challenges and the need for programmatic adjustments reflects a nuanced understanding of the complexities involved in translating policy intentions into meaningful outcomes on the ground.

A. Significance of the topics/issues to the field of research		
Extremely significant	10	X
Important	8	
Modest	6	
Trivial	4	
Unimportant	2	
B. Value of writing and other elements (figures, tables, graphical elements)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
C. Conceptual consistency (clarity of objectives, treatment of relevant literature, consistency of reasoning, argumentation)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
D. Methodological consistency (research design, sampling, data collection/analyses as relevant to qualitative/quantitative data)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
E. General discussion and conclusions (implications, limitations, future research, recommendations)		
Superior	10	X
Good	8	
Minor problems	6	
Major problems	4	
Completely inadequate	2	
F. Paper's contribution to the research field		
Extremely significant	10	X
Important	8	
Modest	6	
Trivial	4	
Unimportant	2	
Recommendations		
Accept unconditionally, without the necessity of major content and structure adjustments	(55-60)	X
Accept conditionally, subject to minor revision, according to the accompanying comments	(50-54)	
Encourage revision, according to the accompanying comments	(40-49)	
Reject in current form, but allow resubmission of a substantially different version, according to the accompanying comments	(25-39)	
Reject unconditionally, because the likelihood of a successful revision is remote	(<24)	

B. Conclusion

The research work has a good value of conceptual consistency and a very good coverage of the planned topic, a good research design, and clarity of the objectives.

The article is **ACCEPTED** for publication unconditionally, without the necessity of major content and structure adjustments.

C. Remarks

a. Article's formatting

Some minor aesthetic adjustments (formatting) will be performed during the editing phase:

- formatting of the title: (font size, font type, font case, position, spacing, and indentation);
- formatting of authors' name and affiliation (editing, font type, font size, font case, position);
- header/footer editing (adding authors' names and article's title, editing page number, and adding correspondence email address). Previously added footers/endnotes will be preserved and (or) actualized;
- adding the reserved DOI; abstract, keywords content formatting: (font size, font type, font case, position, spacing and indentation, paragraphs editing);
- tables, figures, images, diagrams formatting (size, border, font size, font type, font case, position);
- in-text citation and reference list formatting (font size, font type, font case, position, style, spacing and indentation, hyperlinks editing and verification).

The content editing will be done by the editors.

b. Content adjustments

The content of the submitted manuscript will be changed only after the editing phase and after being communicated as a recommended content update to the authors. The recommended content adjustments are meant to be made by the author; if, for various reasons, the authors consider the editor intervention more appropriate, these adjustments can be made by the editors in the editing phase.

c. Edited article adjustments/updates

Before the publication, the article is sent back to the authors, in an editable for (Word DOCX file format). Last content updates, minor corrections can be made by the author(s) in this phase, without affecting the document structure and formatting. We highly recommend the author's contribution to this last phase; by that, the resulting document has the authors' final agreement on the article's form and content.

The following sections/elements need to be included in the article (updated, if necessary):

- authors(s) affiliation as: position, department, institution, country. If necessary, more affiliations can be included.
- a correspondence email address. If necessary, more email addresses can be included.
- a Conflict of Interest statement
- an About the Author(s) section containing: author(s) academic, position, education, participation, achievements, links to academic institutional webpages, and/or academic networks (Academia.edu, ResearchGate, ORCID, etc.)

Note: For non-English articles, the inclusion of a translated title, abstract, and keywords is recommended (for indexing purposes).

The following sections are required only if the authors decide on their inclusion:

- funding statements;
- ethic statements, acknowledgments;
- authors' participation in the elaboration of the research;

- study limitations, acknowledgments, etc.

d. Publication of the article

When having the final form, the article is published in the current issue (there is no waiting time for the publication of a new issue). The publication of the article is communicated to the authors via email; the email includes the following:

- a copy of the published article (as a PDF file) identical with the one published in the journal;
- a certificate of publication (as a PDF file);
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